

Practical Considerations For System-Level Simulators of UNB IoT Devices Over LEO Satellites

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Abstract

The evaluation of the protocols in wireless systems is generally carried out by means of simulations. However, the large number of parameters of the radio link introduces a tradeoff between complexity and accuracy. This is the case of the system-level simulation of Ultra Narrow Band (UNB) signals over Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites. In order to overcome the complexity issue of this scenario, the proposed system-level simulator implements: i) physical layer abstraction methods, ii) sliding window strategies and iii) parallel architectures. Regarding the validness of the system-level simulations, it is necessary to have an accurate model of the physical layer. In particular, the system-level simulator has to know feasible pulse-shape filters, the minimum SINR at which the received data can be decoded, or the maximum collision bandwidth. Towards this regard, we have resorted to: i) convex optimization techniques for designing pulse-shape FIR filters with the frequency selectivity that the UNB signals require, ii) the Chi-square test for detecting the UNB frames with a predefined probability of false alarm, and iii) Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) and Least Squares (LS) strategies for devising coarse and fine Carrier Frequency Offset (CFO) estimation algorithms. Furthermore, we explain how to compute the closed-form of the collision region between two UNB frames with time and frequency diversity in order to speed up system-level simulation. Results show that for SINRs larger than 8.5 dB it is possible to compensate the time and frequency drifts of IoT UNB signals over LEO, attain a BER lower than $1 \cdot 10^{-3}$, detect the UNB frames with a probability of false alarm of 0.01%, and design pulse-shape FIR filters with a moderate number of coefficients.

I. INTRODUCTION

UNB systems exploit time and frequency diversity by resorting to the so-called random time-frequency ALOHA protocol [1], [2]. In order to simulate this protocol in the satellite domain is not an easy task. The large number of IoT devices jointly with the great size of the satellite footprint make difficult to evaluate the performance of Random Access (RA) protocols. In order to overcome these drawbacks we have resorted to the physical layer abstraction proposed in [3] but introducing the satellite footprint information and the Doppler model. Moreover, we have taken advantage of the sliding window concept proposed in [4]. A recursive window that moves continuously around the observation time. However, the system-level simulators have to provide realistic results. Towards, this regard, the system-level simulator needs to use an accurate model of the physical layer [3]. In particular, the required SINR threshold for correctly decoding the packets or the pulse-shape filter to use. For that reason we have used convex theory to implement feasible pulse-shape filters, devised an strategy for detecting the UNB frames with a predefined false alarm probability, and developed coarse and fine carrier frequency offset estimators for compensating the frequency drifts of UNB IoT signals over a LEO channel.

Numerical results show that for a Doppler rate $f_{r_{d,k}} \in [0, \dots, 25]$ Hz/s, and a residual frequency shift of $f_k[0] = 10$ Hz, it is possible to attain a target BER of $0.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ when the SINR is larger than 8.5 dB. We have considered that the satellite is an altitude of $h = 600$ Km, the number of time replicas of the time-frequency ALOHA protocol is three, $n_r = 3$.

The rest of the paper is distributed as follows. Section II introduces the models of the interference and frequency drifts of UNB IoT signals over LEO satellite. Section III explains how it is possible to design UNB pulse-shape filters using convex theory in an easy way. Next, in Section IV is detailed the coarse and fine carrier frequency offset compensation schemes. Finally, Section V presents the system-level UNB simulator, and Section VI draws the conclusions.

II. SIGNAL MODEL

In this section we introduce the model of the interference and the frequency drifts of a UNB IoT signal over LEO satellite. These two signal models are key to implement a system-level simulator with realistic results.

A. Interference Model

If we suppose that there are N users that access to a LEO satellite, then the aggregated received signal can be formulated as:

$$r_k(t) = \underbrace{h_k(t) \star s_k(t) \star g(f_k, t)}_{\text{Desired Signal}} + \underbrace{\sum_{q \neq k}^{N-2} h_q(t) \star s_q(t) \star g(f_q, t)}_{\text{Interference Signals}} + n(t), \quad (1)$$

where $s_i(t)$ and $h_i(t)$ represent the information and the channel impulse response for the i -th user, the symbol \star represents the linear convolution and $n(t)$ is the complex Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) of zero mean and variance N_0 . Concerning the waveform, $g(f_i, t)$, is the pulse-shape centered at the frequency f_i , which can be expressed as a function of the low-pass filter $g(t)$ as:

$$g(f_i, t) = g(t) \cdot e^{j2\pi \cdot f_i \cdot t}. \quad (2)$$

Next, to detect the information of the desired user, the received signal of (1) is match filtered as follows:

$$r'(f_k, t) = g(f_k, t)^* \star r_k(t) = \underbrace{h_k(t) \star s_k(t) \star g(f_k, t)^* \star g(f_k, t)}_{\text{Desired Signal}} + \underbrace{\sum_{q \neq k}^{N-2} h_q(t) \star s_q(t) \star g(f_k, t)^* \star g(f_q, t)}_{\text{Interference Signals}} + g(f_k, t)^* \star n(t). \quad (3)$$

Thus, the power of the desired and interference users can be equated as:

$$P_r = \underbrace{|h_k|^2 \cdot P_0}_{\text{Power of the Desired User}} + \underbrace{\sum_{q \neq k} |h_q|^2 \cdot |\beta(\Delta f_{k,q})|^2 \cdot P_0}_{\text{Power of the Interference Users}} + P_n, \quad (4)$$

being P_0 and P_n the power of the transmitted signal and the filtered noise respectively. The term $\beta(\Delta f_{k,q})$ is the attenuation that experiments the power of the q -th interference when its frequency separation respect to one of the desired user is $\Delta f_{k,q}$, i.e. $\Delta f_{k,q} = |f_k - f_q|$. The coefficient $\beta(\Delta f_{k,q})$ reduces the interference level and so it can also be understood as a rejection filter [7]. The coefficient $\beta(\Delta f_{k,q})$ is the unity when the interference and the desired users have the same frequency, i.e. $\beta(\Delta f_{k,q} = 0) = 1$. The design of this rejection filter for UNB signals is a challenging task since its bandwidth is quite small. For that reason, Section III explains how to do it in an easy way by means of convex tools.

B. Frequency drifts model

If IoT devices use UNB techniques to transmit data, then the Jitter of the oscillator is not negligible. Furthermore, in LEO satellite communications we have to take into account one additional source of distortion, the Doppler effects. Consequently, the q -th symbol of the transmitted signal for the desired user will be received with the following frequency:

$$f_{r,k}[q] = f_{t,k} + \Delta f_{Jitter,k}[q] + \Delta f_{Doppler,k}[q], \quad (5)$$

where $f_{t,k}$ and $f_{r,k}$ are the transmitted and received carrier frequency of the desired user. The terms $\Delta f_{Jitter,k}$ and $\Delta f_{Doppler,k}$ represent the frequency variations due to the Jitter and Doppler effects. During the transmission of a frame, we have assumed that all values are time-invariant except for the Doppler effects. Let $f_{d,k}$ and $f_{r_{d,k}}$ be the Doppler shift and Doppler rate. Then, the frequency drift due to the Doppler effects is modeled as [11]:

$$\Delta f_{Doppler,k}[q] = f_{d,k} + f_{r_{d,k}} \cdot q \cdot T_{SAM}, \quad (6)$$

being T_{SAM} the sampling period. If we plug (6) into (5), then the received frequency at the q -th time instant of the frame becomes:

$$f_k[q] = f_k[0] + f_{r_{d,k}} \cdot q \cdot T_{SAM}, \quad (7)$$

where $f_k[0]$ encompasses all time-invariant frequency drifts in a frame:

$$f_k[0] = f_{t,k} + \Delta f_{Jitter,k} + f_{d,k} \quad (8)$$

Regarding the Jitter we have modeled it as a random variable uniformly distributed in the following interval [1], [2]:

$$\Delta f_{Jitter,k} \in [-f_{t,k} \cdot \sigma_{Jitter} \dots f_{t,k} \cdot \sigma_{Jitter}], \quad (9)$$

being σ_{Jitter} the maximum deviation of the Jitter. In our case we have assumed that its value is $\sigma_{Jitter} = 25$ ppm according to [8].

III. PULSE-SHAPE DESIGN

As we have reported in Section II, the pulse-shape reduces the interference level. However, the small bandwidth of the UNB signals and the large selectivity that it is required to the UNB pulse-shape filters complicates their design. In order to overcome this drawback, we have resorted to convex optimization techniques since they allows us to approach a predetermined function in an easy way [9]. By doing so, we have rewritten the rejection coefficient, $\beta[\Delta f_{k,q}]$, as:

$$\beta(\Delta f_{k,q}) = g(f, t)^* \star g(f + \Delta f_{k,q}, t) = \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} g_l^* g_l \cdot e^{j2\pi \cdot \Delta f_{k,q} \cdot l} = \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} |g_l|^2 \cdot e^{j2\pi \cdot \Delta f_{k,q} \cdot l}, \quad (10)$$

where g_l is the l -th coefficient of the pulse-shape, and L is its number of coefficients. At this point, we have considered that the coefficients of the pulse-shape are obtained from a predefined rejection filter, so-called mask, β . In this regard, references [1], [5]- [7], provide the linear and logarithmic mask of the rejection coefficients, β . We have used this mask to obtain the rejection and pulse-shape filters. Let us stack column-wise the coefficients as follows: $\beta = [\beta(\Delta f_0), \dots, \beta(\Delta f_q), \dots, \beta(\Delta f_{m-1})]^T$. Then, the coefficients of the pulse-shape filter, denoted as $\mathbf{b} = [b_0, \dots, b_{L-1}]^T$, are obtained by solving:

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 \\ 1 & e^{j2\pi \cdot \Delta f_1} & \dots & e^{j2\pi \cdot \Delta f_1 \cdot (L-1)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & e^{j2\pi \cdot \Delta f_{m-1}} & \dots & e^{j2\pi \cdot \Delta f_{m-1} \cdot (L-1)} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{H}} \cdot \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} |g_0|^2 \\ |g_1|^2 \\ \vdots \\ |g_{L-1}|^2 \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{b}} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \beta[\Delta f_0] \\ \beta[\Delta f_1] \\ \vdots \\ \beta[\Delta f_{m-1}] \end{bmatrix}}_{\beta} \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{H} \cdot \mathbf{b} = \beta, \quad (11)$$

being m the number of frequency points. In particular, the relationship between the coefficients of the rejection filter and the pulse-shape is:

$$b_p = |g_p|^2 \quad \forall p = 0, \dots, L-1. \quad (12)$$

To solve (11) we have assumed that: i) the pulse-shape exhibits symmetry, i.e. $g(p) = g(L-p) \quad \forall p : 0 \dots L-1$, and ii) the number of coefficients of the pulse-shape, i.e. L , is odd. By doing so, we can reformulate the matrix \mathbf{H} as:

$$\mathbf{H}_{\text{New}}(p, :) = \mathbf{H}(p, :) \cdot e^{-j2\pi \cdot \Delta f_p \cdot \frac{L-1}{2}} \Rightarrow |\mathbf{H}_{\text{New}}(p, :)| = |\mathbf{H}(p, :)|, \quad (13)$$

where the index p and Δf_p represent the p -th row of the matrix \mathbf{H} and the frequency separation respectively. By considering (13), the system of equations presented in (11) can be solved by means of convex optimization tools. In particular, we have resorted to the CVX toolbox. CVX is a @MATLAB software for disciplined convex programming [9]. The following optimization problem obtains the mask of a symmetric rejection filter by solving the weighted-least squares metric:

$$\underset{\mathbf{b}}{\text{minimize}} \sum_{p=0}^{m-1} \|\mathbf{W} \cdot (\mathbf{H}_{\text{New}}(p, :) \cdot \mathbf{b} - \beta(\Delta f_p))\|. \quad (14)$$

where $\mathbf{W} = \text{diag}(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\beta(\Delta f_p)}})$. Note that the cost function of (14) corresponds to the estimation error normalized by the value of the mask. By doing so, it is possible to obtain accurate estimations for the lowest values of the rejection filter, β . Thus, after evaluating (14) we obtain the vector \mathbf{b} and the pulse-shape \mathbf{g} by means of (12). In order to asses that the mask of the rejection filter β is correctly estimated, we have recomputed it by means of the convolution expression of (10) and its matrix relationship equated in (11). Fig. 1 shows the rejection mask when the number of coefficients is $L=91$ (Fig. 1a) and $L=191$ (Fig. 1b) using (10) and (11). From there we observe that for $L=91$ the estimated rejection filter follows quite well its mask except in its nulls. Towards this regard, we have increased the number its coefficients to $L=191$. Finally, Fig. 2a and Fig. 2b show the coefficients of the rejection and pulse-shape filters when the number of coefficients is $L=191$.

IV. FRAME-DETECTION PROCEDURE

To efficiently detect the UNB signals we have applied the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) to the received samples, computed the average power of each bin [2], [6] and applied the Chi-square test to them. Let $\mathbf{r} = [r[0], \dots, r[N_{DFT}-1]]^T$ be the vector that stacks the samples at the input of the DFT, and N_{DFT} is the number of points of the DFT. Thus the q -th output of the DFT, denoted as $z[q]$, can be described as:

$$z[q] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_{DFT}}} \sum_{p=0}^{N_{DFT}-1} r[p] e^{-j2\pi \cdot \frac{p \cdot q}{N_{DFT}}}, \quad (15)$$

for $q = 0, \dots, N_{DFT} - 1$. Then, the energy at the q -th bin after processing M DFTs is:

$$P_{z[q]} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{l=0}^{M-1} |z_l[q]|^2, \quad (16)$$

Figure 1: Estimated rejection filter β in dB

Figure 2: Estimated rejection and pulse-shape filters in the time domain when the number of coefficients is L=191

being $z_l[q]$ the q -th output of the l -th DFT block. After that we need to compare the computed energy from (16) with a threshold. This step is computed by means of the so-called Chi-square test [10] (See Fig. 3). This test formulates the next two hypotheses:

$$\begin{aligned} H_0 &\implies \text{The } q\text{-th bin of the DFT only contains noise} \implies z_l[q] = w_l[q] \\ H_1 &\implies \text{The } q\text{-th bin of the DFT contains signal and noise} \implies z_l[q] = y_l[q] + w_l[q], \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where $y_l[q]$ is the desired signal and $w_l[q]$ is the additive white complex Gaussian noise at the q -th bin of the l -th processed DFT. The magnitude of the threshold has to be set up to minimize the probability of deciding H_1 when H_0 is true, which is referred to as the Probability of False Alarm (PAF). Towards this regard, we know that if the noise is complex Gaussian distributed, then the sum of M norms of an AWGN noise follows a Chi-square distribution with $2 \cdot M$ degrees of freedom. Thus, the Probability Density Function (PDF) of (16) when the hypothesis H_0 is true, i.e. there is only noise in the q -th bin of the DFT, is:

$$PDF(P_{z[q]=w[q]} = \xi) = p\left(P_{z[q]=w[q]} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{l=0}^{M-1} |w_l[q]|^2\right) = \frac{\xi^{M-1} \cdot e^{-\frac{\xi}{2}}}{M \cdot 2^M \cdot \Gamma(2 \cdot M)}, \quad (18)$$

being ξ the value that takes the noise power and Γ the complete gamma function [11]. If the q -th bin of the DFT only contains noise, then the probability that the average power of the received samples, $P_{w[q]}$, be lower than a particular threshold,

Figure 3: Frame detection procedure using Chi-square test.

(a) PDF of the Chi-square distribution with $2 \cdot M$ degrees of freedom.

(b) CDF of the Chi-square distribution with $2 \cdot M$ degrees of freedom.

Figure 4: PDF and CDF of the Chi-square distribution with $2 \cdot M$ degrees of freedom.

denoted as ξ_T , is determined by the CDF of (16), which it is:

$$CDF(2 \cdot M, \xi_T) = p(P_{z[q]=w[q]} \leq \xi_T) = \int_0^{\xi_T} \frac{\xi^{M-1} \cdot e^{-\frac{\xi}{2}}}{M \cdot 2^M \cdot \Gamma(2 \cdot M)} d\xi = \frac{\gamma(M, \xi_T/2)}{M \cdot \Gamma(M)}. \quad (19)$$

The symbol $\gamma(a, b)$ represents the incomplete gamma function [11]. Fig. 4a and Fig. 4b show the theoretical and practical values of the PDF and CDF of (18) and (19) when the number of averaged samples goes from $M=2$ to $M=7$ respectively. Note in both figures that their theoretical and practical values perfectly match. In (19) we have assumed that if (16) is lower than the threshold ξ_T , then the q -th bin of the DFT only has noise, i.e. the hypothesis H_0 is true. Otherwise, the receiver assumes that the desired signal is present at the q -th bin of the DFT, i.e. the hypothesis H_0 is false. For that reason the threshold ξ_T has to be selected with care to minimize the probability of false alarm, which it is determined as,

$$PFA(P_{z[q]} > \xi_T) = \int_{\xi_T}^{\infty} p(\xi) d\xi = 1 - \int_0^{\xi_T} \frac{\xi^{M-1} \cdot e^{-\frac{\xi}{2}}}{M \cdot 2^M \cdot \Gamma(2 \cdot M)} d\xi = 1 - \frac{\gamma(M, \xi_T/2)}{M \cdot \Gamma(M)} = 1 - CDF(2 \cdot M, \xi_T). \quad (20)$$

At this point, Table I gathers the value of the threshold ξ_T to achieve a PFA of 1%, 0.1% and 0.01% when the averaged samples goes from $M = 2$ to $M = 30$ in steps of 7 samples, and the noise power is the unity. If we had a different noise power, i.e. N_0 , then the threshold of the Chi-square test should be normalized as:

$$\xi_{T, N_0} = \xi_T \cdot N_0 \quad (21)$$

Next, to determine M we have considered that the peak at the output of the DFT is kept unchanged when performing the frame detection procedure. It means that we have computed the minimum and maximum frequency drifts of the M samples

for the k -th user at the j -th bin of the DFT, denoted as $f_{0,k,j}$ and $f_{M-1,k,j}$, their difference, and impose that it has to be lower than the frequency separation of the DFT, symbolized by Δf_{DFT} , as :

$$\left. \begin{aligned} f_{0,k,j} &= f_{k,j}[0] \\ f_{M-1,k,j} &= f_{k,j}[0] + M \cdot N_{DFT} \cdot f_{r_{d,k}} \cdot T_{SAM} \end{aligned} \right\} \rightarrow f_{M-1,k,j} - f_{0,k,j} < \frac{\Delta f_{DFT}}{\rho} \rightarrow M < \frac{\Delta f_{DFT}}{N_{DFT} \cdot f_{r_{d,k}} \cdot T_{SAM} \cdot \rho} \quad (22)$$

being ρ a safety parameter for assuring that the peak of the M samples does not move from the same bin. As it is possible to observe, the larger the Doppler rate, the lower the number of samples to take in the frame detection. Thus, the procedure to obtain the threshold ξ_T , would be: i) to compute the number of samples M by using (22), ii) to evaluate (20) for a predetermined probability of false alarm, and iii) normalize the obtained threshold, ξ_T by the corresponding noise variance N_0 according to (21). After detecting the frames, we need to synchronize them. The following section details how to carry out this process in an UNB system.

V. SYNCHRONIZATION

Regarding the synchronization stage, we have evaluated the coarse and fine carrier frequency offset for the UNB frames. The following subsections explain them.

A. Coarse Carrier Frequency Offset Estimation

As we have explained in Section IV, the UNB frames are detected using the DFT. This means that if a UNB signal is detected at the q -th bin of the DFT, $q \in [0, \dots, N_{DFT} - 1]$, then the estimated carrier frequency, denoted as \hat{f}_k , is:

$$\hat{f}_k = f_{min} + q \cdot \Delta f_{DFT} \quad (23)$$

where f_{min} is the minimum frequency to sense and Δf_{DFT} is the DFT frequency separation, which it is expressed as:

$$\Delta f_{DFT} = \frac{BW_S}{N_{DFT}}, \quad (24)$$

being BW_S the bandwidth that the receiver has to sense. Thus, if the hypothesis H_1 is true, i.e. there is signal at the q -th bin of the DFT, then the error in the estimation of the frequency of the desired user, denoted as f_k , is bounded to:

$$e_{DFT} = |f_k - \hat{f}_k| \leq \frac{\Delta f_{DFT}}{2}, \quad (25)$$

where f_k is the frequency of the desired user. The error in its estimation is due to the frequency drifts of the Doppler effects, Jitter and also to the DFT resolution. In order to minimize the estimation error of the frequency of the desired user we have considered that the coarse CFO estimation compensates the time-invariant frequency offset, i.e. $f_k[0]$. By doing so, the number of DFT points, N_{DFT} , is ruled by:

$$f_{k,j}[0] < \frac{\Delta f_{DFT}}{\varrho} \implies N_{DFT} > \frac{BW_S}{f_{k,j}[0] \cdot \varrho}, \quad (26)$$

being ϱ a safeguard parameter for having a low estimation error in the frequency of the first symbol of the frame. However, due to the finite resolution of the DFT and the presence of a Doppler rate, there is a residual frequency drift after the coarse CFO compensation that degrades the BER. Towards this regard, Fig. 5 provides the BER for the BPSK and DBPSK modulations when the SNR is 8, 8.5 and 9 dB, the carrier frequency is $f_k = 10$ KHz, the sampling frequency is $f_{SAM} = 100$ KHz. The CFO goes from 0 to 0.01% of the carrier frequency. If the target BER is $1 \cdot 10^{-3}$, then the maximum CFO that can be supported is 0.003% for $SNR = 8$ dB and 0.004% for $SNR = 9$ dB. These results highlight that a fine carrier frequency estimator offset is needed. The details about it are provided in the following section.

Table I: Values of the threshold ξ_T to have a PFA of 0.01,0.001 and 0.0001

Number of Averaged Samples	PFA=0.01	PFA=0.001	PFA=0.0001
$M = 2$	6.6385	9.2335	11.7565
$M = 9$	3.8673	4.7014	5.4656
$M = 16$	3.3429	3.9055	4.4108
$M = 23$	3.0957	3.5392	3.9330
$M = 30$	2.9460	3.3203	3.6501

Figure 5: BER of BPSK and DBPSK modulations when there is a residual carrier frequency offset.

B. Fine Carrier Frequency Offset Estimation

The derivation of the fine CFO estimation departs from the frequency drift model of (7). According to this model the value of the phase for the q -th sample will be:

$$\Phi_k[q] = 2\pi f_k[q] \cdot q \cdot T_S + \theta_k[q] + \phi_{0,k}, \quad (27)$$

where $\theta_k[q]$ is the phase of the q -th symbol and $\phi_{0,k}$ the initial phase offset for the desired user. In order to estimate the residual frequency shift of the symbols we have resorted to the pilots of the synchronization sequence. At this step it has been assumed that the boundaries of the frame are perfectly estimated [12], [13]. Thus, if the field of frame synchronization has N_p pilots, then we can set this system of equations from (27), namely

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \Phi_k[q_0] - \theta_k[q_0] \\ \Phi_k[q_0 + 1] - \theta_k[q_0 + 1] \\ \vdots \\ \Phi_k[q_0 + N_p - 1] - \theta_k[q_0 + N_p - 1] \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{\Phi}} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 2\pi \cdot q_0 \cdot T_S & 2\pi \cdot q_0^2 \cdot T_S^2 & 1 \\ 2\pi \cdot (q_0 + 1) \cdot T_S & 2\pi \cdot (q_0 + 1)^2 \cdot T_S^2 & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 2\pi \cdot (q_0 + N_p - 1) \cdot T_S & 2\pi \cdot (q_0 + N_p - 1)^2 \cdot T_S^2 & 1 \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{H}} \cdot \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \hat{f}_k[0] \\ \hat{f}_{r,d,k} \\ \hat{\phi}_{0,k} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{p}}. \quad (28)$$

Note that the phase of the pilots is known. Therefore, it can be removed from the received signal as it is shown in (28). There we have denoted by q_0 the position of the first pilot in the frame, $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 1}$ is the vector of variables to estimate, $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_p \times 3}$ is the matrix that weights the parameters and $\mathbf{\Phi} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_p \times 1}$ is the phase of the received signal in the pilot positions. In order to solve this system of equations we have applied the well-known Least Squares (LS) method [11], giving rise to

$$\mathbf{p} = (\mathbf{H}^H \mathbf{H})^{-1} \mathbf{H}^H \mathbf{\Phi} = \mathbf{H}^\# \mathbf{\Phi}, \quad (29)$$

being $\mathbf{H}^\# \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times N_p}$ the pseudoinverse of the matrix \mathbf{H} . After computing (28) we have the estimation of the initial frequency shift, denoted as $\hat{f}[q]$, the Doppler rate, $\hat{f}_{r,d,k}$ and the phase offset $\hat{\phi}$. Therefore, the estimated instantaneous phase will be:

$$\hat{\Phi}_k[q] = 2\pi \hat{f}_k[0] \cdot q \cdot T_S + 2\pi \hat{f}_{r,d,k}[0] \cdot q^2 \cdot T_S^2 + \hat{\phi}_{0,k}. \quad (30)$$

This phase shift has to be applied to the output samples of the matched filter to remove the residual carrier frequency offset as follows:

$$\hat{s}_k[q] = s_k[q] \cdot e^{j \cdot (\Phi_k[q] - \hat{\Phi}_k[q])} + w_k[q], \quad (31)$$

where $s_k[q]$ and $\hat{s}_k[q]$ represent the q -th transmitted symbol and its estimation for the desired user after the fine CFO compensation, whereas $w_k[q]$ is the resulting noise after the compensation. Finally, Fig. 6 shows the BER of the payload when the number of pilots is $N_p = 29$ bits and different SNRs, i.e. 8, 8.5 and 9 dB. The Doppler rate varies from 0 to 25 Hz/s in steps of 1 Hz/s and there is a frequency shift of $f_k[0] = 10$ Hz. From these results we have concluded that the minimum SNR to achieve a target BER of $1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ is 8.5 dB. Note also that the LS estimation is able to remove the major part of the residual frequency drift. Specially, the frequency variation that introduces the Doppler rate.

Figure 6: BER payload.

Figure 7: Collision Regions for the three replicas.

VI. SYSTEM-LEVEL UNB SIMULATION

In order to perform system level simulations in LEO satellites we have resorted to the sliding window approach and the analysis of the time-frequency overlapped region between users. The sliding window approach is a window that moves continuously around the observation time. Its minimum duration, denoted as T_{SW} , in the ALOHA protocol is three frames [4], [14]. Thus, if T_F denotes the time duration of a frame (replicas included), then the sliding window duration will be $T_{SW} = 3 \cdot T_F$.

To determine the collisions we need to compute the time and frequencies spanned by each replica of a frame. In a system with Doppler rate, the received frequency of the k -th user at the l -th replica, denoted as $f_{r,l,k}$ has the following model:

$$f_{r,l,k}[q] = f_{l,k}[q_{l,k}] + f_{r,d,l,k} \cdot (q - q_{l,k}) \cdot T_S, \quad (32)$$

where $q_{l,k}$ is the delay of the first symbol of the l -th replica respect to the starting point of the sliding window (See Fig. 7), $f_{l,k}[q_{l,k}]$ is the frequency shift of the first sample of the l -th replica (See Fig. 7) and it is: $f_{l,k}[q_{l,k}] = f_{t,l,k} + \Delta f_{Jitter_k} + f_{d,l,k}$ (See (5),(7)). The terms $f_{t,l,k}$, $f_{d,l,k}$ and $f_{r,d,l,k}$ are the carrier frequency, Doppler frequency shift and rate of the k -th user at the l -th replica. Thus, let BW_C be the maximum frequency for assuming that two users overlap in frequency. In this case, two users frequency overlap at the l -th replica when the difference between their frequencies is lower than:

$$|f_{l,k}[q] - f_{l,i}[q]| \leq BW_C. \quad (33)$$

In order to obtain closed-form expressions of (33) we have to know the possible cases of collision that we could have. Fig. 7 plots the frequencies for each one of the three replicas of the two users. There the symbol $\Delta_{l,k,i}$ is the difference between the access time of the k -th and i -th users at the l -th replica, i.e. $\Delta_{l,k,i} = q_{l,i} - q_{l,k}$. From Fig. 7 it is possible to observe that only in the regions R_2 and R_3 could exist any frequency that satisfies (33). Next, if we particularize (32) for the k -th and i -th users (See Table II), and plug them into (33), then we obtain the cross-points between two overlapped users, denoted as q_C , in Table III.

Table II: Frequencies of the users that intersect

Region	Frequencies of User k and User i
R_2	User k $f_k[q] = f_k[q_{l,k}] + fr_{l,k} \cdot (q - q_{l,k} - \Delta_{l,k,i}) \cdot T_S$ User i $f_i[q] = f_i[q_{l,i}] + fr_{l,i} \cdot (q - q_{l,i}) \cdot T_S$
R_3	User k $f_k[q] = f_k[q_{l+1,k}] + fr_{l+1,k} \cdot (q - q_{l+1,k}) \cdot T_S$ User i $f_i[q] = f_i[q_{l,i}] + fr_{l,i} \cdot (q - q_{l,i} - N + \Delta_{l,k,i}) \cdot T_S$

Table III: Cross-points of the users that intersect

Reg.	Cross-points between the k -th and i -th users
R_2	$q_C \leq \frac{BW_C + f_i[q_{l,i}] - f_k[q_{l,k}] + (q_{l,i} fr_{l,i} - q_{l,k} fr_{l,k}) T_S - \Delta_{l,k,i}}{T_S \cdot (fr_{l,k} - fr_{l,i})}$ or $q_C \leq \frac{BW_C + f_k[q_{l,k}] - f_i[q_{l,i}] + (q_{l,k} fr_{l,k} - q_{l,i} fr_{l,i}) T_S + \Delta_{l,k,i}}{T_S \cdot (fr_{l,i} - fr_{l,k})}$ Being $0 \leq q_C < N - \Delta_{l,k,i}$
R_3	$q_C \leq \frac{BW_C + f_i[q_{l,i}] - f_k[q_{l+1,k}] + \Sigma_{l,k,i}}{T_S \cdot (fr_{l+1,k} - fr_{l,i})}$ or $q_C \leq \frac{BW_C + f_k[q_{l+1,k}] - f_i[q_{l,i}] + \Psi_{l,k,i}}{T_S \cdot (fr_{l+1,k} - fr_{l,i})}$ Being $N - \Delta_{l,k,i} \leq q_C < N$, with $\Omega_{l,k,i} = N - \Delta_{l,k,i}$ and $\Sigma_{l,k,i} = -(q_{l+1,k} fr_{l+1,k} - (q_{l,i} - N + \Delta_{l,k,i}) fr_{l,i}) \cdot T_S$ $\Psi_{l,k,i} = (q_{l+1,k} fr_{l+1,k} - (q_{l,i} - N + \Delta_{l,k,i}) fr_{l,i}) \cdot T_S$

In order to run the simulations, it is necessary to set up the number of UNB IoT devices that are ready to transmit in the satellite footprint, the SINR threshold to correctly demodulate the packets and the Jitter and the Doppler effects that impair the transmission. The UNB IoT devices access to the channel using the random time-frequency ALOHA protocol. That means that in a channel access attempt they send the original packet and $n_r - 1$ consecutive replicas in different frequencies and consecutive time instants. After that it is computed the footprint of the LEO satellite. Next, for each active terminal it is determined the arrival time, the attenuation, the Jitter of the oscillator, the Doppler shift and the Doppler rate. Bearing in mind this information, the simulator computes the number of packets that are correctly demodulated in a predetermined observation time window. The algorithm 1 shows the corresponding algorithm of the system-level simulator. Finally, in order to speed up the simulation we have parallelized its loops by resorting to mex-functions and message passing algorithm [15], [16]. System-level simulations provide the number of detected users taking advantage of power unbalance. By doing so, the results show that for a criterion of 99.9%, which means that only 1 out 1000 packets is lost, and that the terminals generate 1 packet every 20 minutes, then it is possible to correctly detect up to 19.230,76 users (See Table IV).

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have evaluated: i) the design of the pulse-shape filter for UNB signals using convex theory, ii) the frame detection procedure considering a predefined false alarm probability, and iii) the coarse and fine carrier frequency offset estimators. The design of pulse-shape filters using convex theory shows that it is possible to obtain linear phase FIR filters with a moderate number of coefficients with a large selectivity. The frame detection resorts to the DFT technique to discriminate the signal from the noise given a probability of false alarm. By doing so, we obtain a coarse estimation of the carrier frequency offset and set up the maximum SINR that it can support to estimate correctly the bin of the desired user. The frame detection procedure considers a DFT of $N_{DFT} = 16K$ points, a sensed bandwidth of $BW_S = 200$ KHz, and a false alarm probability of 0.01%. In order to carry out the fine carrier frequency offset compensation, we have implemented the Least Squares (LS) of the phase shift. The results show that for a Doppler rate $fr_{d,k} \in [0, \dots, 25]$ Hz/s, and a residual frequency shift of $f_k[0] = 10$ Hz, it is possible to attain a target BER of $1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ when the SNR is at least 8.5 dB. We have considered that the satellite is an altitude of $h = 600$ Km, and that the number of replicas of the time-frequency ALOHA protocol is three, $n_r = 3$. Finally, the simulation results also indicate that for a criterion of 99.9%, which means that only 1 out 1000 packets is lost, and a traffic per terminal of 1 packet every 20 minutes, it is possible to correctly detect up to 19.230,76 users.

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input : Users to simulate, N_u , Maximum Jitter, σ_{Jitter} , and satellite altitude, h

output: Number of detected users

```

1 for  $i \leftarrow 2$  to  $N_{trials}$  do
2   Select the discrete channels
3   Generate the Jitter of the channels
4   Compute the Gain of the User Antenna
5   Compute the Pathloss
6   Compute the Gain of the Satellite Antenna
7   Compute the received power at LEO satellite
8   Pick users inside the Horizon of the satellite
9   Compute the SNR of the users at the satellite
10  Select users with positive link margin
11  Generate Doppler frequencies
12  Select  $N_u$  users from the possible ones
13  Assign access time to the  $N_u$  users
14  for  $j \leftarrow 2$  to  $N_{users}$  do
15    for  $k \leftarrow 3$  to  $N_{users}$  do
16      if Time Collision( $j,k$ ) then
17        TimeCollided( $j$ ) $\leftarrow$  1;
18      if Frequency Collision( $j,k$ ) then
19        FrequencyCollided( $j$ ) $\leftarrow$  1;
20      Compute the Collision Region
21    end
22    if User  $j$  collides then
23      if  $SINR_j > SINR_{target}$  then
24        The collided user can be detected;
25      end
26    end
27 end

```

Algorithm 1: Steps of the system-level simulator

Table IV: Number of detected users for different demodulation probabilities and traffic load

Demod. Prob.	$\frac{1packet}{20min}$	$\frac{1packet}{1h}$	$\frac{1packet}{4h}$	$\frac{1packet}{12h}$	$\frac{1packet}{24h}$
90%	137.077	411.230	1.644.932	4.934.796	9.869.592
95%	95.477	286.431	1.145.725	3.437.176	6.874.352
99%	45.541	136.625	546.502	1.639.507	3.279.014
99.9%	19.230	57.692	230.769	692.307	1.384.614

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